

cos(px)cos(px) from exp(-ipx)exp(ipx) and Maximum Information Transfer?

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In (1) the following problem is considered. A person called A sends information about a value x (in the range of 0 to $3.14/2$) in the form of a special probability function associated with a coin to a person B. (The coin model is used so that the binomial distribution may be employed.) Person B then runs N trials (where $N \rightarrow$ infinite) in order to find positive outcomes for a given x . (1) then shows that the form $\cos(x)\cos(x) = P(x)$, where P is probability, represents the maximum information where information is linked with $\ln(P)$. The objective in (1) is to connect $\cos(x)\cos(x)$ to quantum mechanics and it is stated that $\cos(x)\cos(x)$ is probability that “nature uses to ‘encode’ the polarization angle x ” (1).

Here we consider x instead to represent px , where p is momentum. Then $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ represents a probability associated with a fixed p and x position value. For constant p , $P(x)$ should be the same for all x , but if momentum-motion introduces a probabilistic region i.e. constant/ px , then $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ maximizes information according to (1). If one adds $\sin(px)\sin(px)$ to $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ one obtains $P(x)=1$, i.e. all x points are treated as having the same weight.

One may then consider the two dimensional $\cos(px)+i \sin(px)$ which distinguishes between p and $-p$. Thus regardless of the direction of motion, $\cos(px)$ describes a “probability” to be at x within constant/ p . This maps to a $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ classical type probability which maximizes information (1). We note that given $\exp(ipx)$, one has the relation: $\exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \exp(i (p_1+p_2)x)$. Thus given $\exp(i p x)$, any $p_i + p_j = p$ product probabilities yield the same probability. In other words a given p may be broken into any p_i+p_j i.e. there is a complete loss of information about the constituents. We speculate that this result may be equivalent to the idea that $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ represents maximum information as it does in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $\exp(-e_i/T)\exp(-e_j/T) = \exp(-(e_i+e_j)/T)$.

The Approach of (1)

In (1), a person called A wishes to convey a piece of data information x (in the range 0 to $3.14/2$) to a person B. This is done by encoding x in a probability $P(x)$ associated with a coin. Person B makes N tosses and finds n “heads” results based on the probability $P(x)$ versus $1-P(x)$ i.e. using the binomial distribution. A mutual information is defined in (1) as the “average amount of information” B “gains about x by observing the value n ”. (1) formally defines this as:

$$I(x) = H(n) - H(n/x) \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } H(n) = - \sum \text{over } n P(n) \ln(P(n)) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{with } H(n/x) = (2/ 3.14) \int_0^{3.14/2} dx \{ \sum \text{over } n P(n/p(x)) \ln(P(n/(p(x))) dx \} \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{where } P(n/p) = N! / \{n! (N-n)!\} p^n (1-p)^{N-n} \quad ((4)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$P(n) = (2)/(3.14) \int_0^{3.14/2} P(n/p(x)) dx \quad ((5))$$

{The information that person A has, namely x , ranges from 0 to $3.14/2$.}

$I(x)$ ((2)) is then written as:

$$-\sum_n P(n) \ln(P(n)) + \sum_k w_k \sum_n P(n/p_k) \ln(P(n/p_k)) \quad ((6))$$

where p_k discrete probabilities are used and n ranges from 0 to N where $N \rightarrow$ infinite.

Next $dI/dw_k = 0$ is taken with a Lagrange multiplier b added and (1) writes:

$$-\sum_n P(n/p_k) \ln(P(n)) = b+1 - \sum_n P(n/p_k) \ln(P(n/p_k)) \quad ((7))$$

where $P(n) = \sum_k w_k \ln(P(n/p_k))$

In the large N limit (1) uses $P(n) = 1/N w(n/N)$ and $n = N p_k$

$$\text{Then: } -\ln(w(p_k)/N) = b+1 - \sum_n P(n/p_k) \ln(P(n/p_k)) \quad ((8))$$

$P(n/p_k)$ is the binomial distribution form and one may use Stirling's approximation. This then yields:

$$w(p_k) = 1/(3.14) \cdot 1/\sqrt{p_k(1-p_k)} \quad ((9))$$

((9)) may be made continuous. (1) states that for any p_0 value between 0 and 1, the weight associated with the interval $[p_0, 1]$ is the same as the fraction of 0 to $3.14/2$ that lies within 0 to $x(p_0)$. Thus as (1) shows:

$$x(p_0) = 3.14/2 \int_{(p_0,1)} w(p) dp \quad \text{or } p(x) = \cos(x)\cos(x) \quad ((10)) \quad (\text{see details in (1)}).$$

((1)) notes that $\cos(x)\cos(x)$ is associated with the probability "nature uses to 'encode' the polarization angle θ ". In other words, (1) tries to link $\cos(x)\cos(x)$ to quantum mechanics, but acknowledges that $\cos(x)\cos(x)$ is associated with a real and not complex Hilbert space while quantum mechanics is complex.

Association of $\cos(x)\cos(x)$ with $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$?

We instead try to link x with px where p is momentum and $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = \cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px)$. px is naturally an angle and the range 0 to $3.14/2$ is a quarter of a cycle. The fact that $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$ implies that all x points carry the same weight and that there are two dimensions of probability at the sublevel i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. one may write the ordered pair: $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. In (1) it is acknowledged that $\cos(x)\cos(x)$ is associated with a real Hilbert space and not the complex one of quantum mechanics.

We suggest that the two dimensions of probability are required because one has a dynamical situation. $\cos(px)$ by itself is the same for p and $-p$ and does not distinguish between motion to

the right or left. $\cos(px)$, which is associated with $\cos(px)\cos(px)$, seems to describe a probability scheme within a wavelength constant/ p , but this is a somewhat static picture because it does not show that there are two probability schemes when x changes to $x+\delta x$ as in the case of directional motion.

Thus (1)'s result that $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ maximizes a kind of mutual information seems to apply to the form of the probabilities which make up constant momentum motion, but one needs to add the extra dimension of probability to describe dynamic motion. $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px)$ then ensures that $P(x)=1$ i.e. all x points have the same weight.

$\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2) x)$ and Loss of Information

In (1), calculations are performed to show that $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ represents a maximum information transfer. We ask if this idea of maximum information, i.e. maximum entropy, appears in a different manner. We note that:

$$\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2) x) \quad ((10))$$

Given a specific $p=p_1+p_2$, any $p_i+p_j=p$ have the same product probability. Thus there is a loss of information identical to the Maxwell-Boltzmann case:

$$\exp(-e_i/T) \exp(-e_j/T) = \exp(-(e_i+e_j)/T) \quad ((11))$$

The Maxwell-Boltzmann result is associated with a maximum of entropy subject to a constraint $\sum_i P(e_i)$. We suggest that the form ((10)) may also be associated with a kind of maximum entropy which seems to coincide with the work of (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that (1) calculates a maximum information transfer using ideas of a binomial distribution. (1) finds that $\cos(x)\cos(x)=P(x)$ is the form of probability which maximizes information transfer from one person to another (with ideas of a binomial distribution used) and notes the result is related to polarization angle results in quantum mechanics. (1) also notes that $\cos(x)\cos(x)$ is associated with a real and not complex Hilbert space unlike quantum mechanics.

Here we suggest that $\cos(x)\cos(x)$ represents $\cos(px)\cos(px)$, where p is momentum, which is associated with quantum free particle motion. We suggest that for free motion. each x has the same weight so one must introduce two dimensions i.e. $\cos(px)\cos(px)+\sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$. We argue the two dimensions are linked with dynamic motion. There is a probability distribution linked with $\cos(px)$ which does not distinguish the direction of motion, while a second dimension $\sin(px)$ does. We note that like in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case for which $\exp(-e_i/T)\exp(-e_j/T) = \exp(-(e_i+e_j)/T)$ one has $\exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$. The MB case suggests maximum entropy so we suggest a kind of maximum entropy also associated with $\exp(ipx)$. This seems to be consistent with the ideas of (1) that $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ maximizes information transfer.

References

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